

HAREM STRUCTURE AND REPRODUCTIVE BEHAVIOUR OF *PTEROPUS TONGANUS* IN AMERICAN SAMOA

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We studied the reproductive biology of *Pteropus tonganus* on Tutuila, American Samoa from 1992 to 1994. *Pteropus tonganus* typically roosts in colonies consisting of harem groups averaging 5.3 females per male and peripheral single males and groups of males. The mating system appeared to have elements of both female defense polygyny and resource defense polygyny. The reproductive status of females within harems varied throughout the year so that some females appeared non-pregnant while others were pregnant or nursed large young (up to about 3/4 the length of the female). Post-partum mating was frequent, especially with females that had small dependent young. Mating, pregnancy, birthing, and young of all sizes occurred year-round. However, some evidence of bimodal peaks occurred during January and June-August.

Key words: Flying foxes, *Pteropus tonganus*, Samoa, harems, reproductive behaviour.

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PTEROPUS tonganus has a widespread distribution with populations occurring on the islands off New Guinea, the Solomons, Vanuatu, New Caledonia, Santa Cruz, Fiji, Tonga, Wallis, Futuna, both Samoas, Niue, and Rarotonga and Mangaia of the Cook Islands (Rainey and Pierson 1992). Within American Samoa (14° S, 170° W) *P. tonganus* occurs on 5 of the larger volcanic islands: Tutuila, Aunu'u, Ofu, Olosega, and Ta'u (Figure 1). The largest island, Tutuila (142 km²), is covered with primary rainforest, secondary forest, and agricultural plantations and contains the largest population of *P. tonganus*.

P. tonganus is a medium sized flying-fox with no conspicuous size dimorphism (Miller and Wilson 1997). It has a wing span of about 1 m and a weight of 300-500 g (Craig *et al.* 1994; pers. obs.). It is colonial and occurs in daytime roosts of up to several thousand individuals (Craig *et al.* 1994; Banack 1996; Pierson *et al.* 1996). At dusk flying-foxes leave the roost to forage upon flowers, nectar,

and fruit of trees in agroforest plantations as well as in primary and secondary forests (Banack 1996; Pierson *et al.* 1996). Nocturnal feeding sites may be up to 20 km from the roost (Banack 1996).

Little has been previously recorded concerning the reproductive biology of *P. tonganus*. Among other tropical and subtropical Megachiroptera, considerable variation has been shown to occur with respect to the seasonality of breeding (O'Brien 1993) and the variety of mating systems used (Neuweiler 1969; Cheke and Dahl 1981; Wiles 1987; Carroll and Mace 1988; Pierson and Rainey 1992). Hence, the present study which ran for two years from September 1992 to August 1994, on Tutuila Island, American Samoa, was concerned with determining the reproductive behaviour of *P. tonganus* and the mating system used by this flying-fox.

Figure 1. Map of the seven islands of American Samoa and neighbouring Western Samoa. Within American Samoa, *Pteropus tonganus* occurred on all islands except Swains Island and Rose Atoll.

METHODS

Most observations were made at a daytime roost in Olovalu Crater, near the village of Futiga, Tutuila. The site was protected from disturbance by the landowner and the steep volcanic sides prevented entry by most humans. The bats roosted in a variety of trees (*Ficus prolixa*, *Cananga odorata*, *Syzygium* sp.) on the floor and inner walls of this inactive volcano (400 m in diameter). Other roosts on Tutuila were on precipitous cliffs on the north shore or in interior regions without accessing trails or roads. Supplemental observations were made at eleven additional roosts (2-25 km from Olovalu) on Tutuila. With the aid of a Questar telescope at distances ranging from 30-150 m we sexed, aged, and recorded behavioral observations on undisturbed flying-foxes within their roost in Olovalu Crater. All observations were made between 0800 and 1100 hr. The composition and boundaries of harems were determined only where harem trees were sufficiently exposed so that all bats could be seen.

Males were noted as being sexually mature if large testes were visible in the black, descended scrotum and if the penis was relatively large. Immature males had undescended testes and considerably smaller penises. From our observation distance, we could not distinguish between immature and adult females once the immatures attained adult size. The size of the dependent young was scored as: large = about 3/4 the length of an adult, medium = about 1/2 the length of an adult, and small = about 1/4 the length of an adult.

Harem demarcations were ascertained by monitoring male-male encounters at the harem borders, copulations and copulation attempts of harem males and females, and scent-marking behavior of males at territorial boundaries. Inter-bat distance was estimated by using the average length (25 cm) of a hanging bat as our measure. The numbers, sexes, and positions of bats at harem trees were quantified twice a month (intervals between visits varied due to frequent inclement weather) over a two-year period.

Fig. 2. *Pteropus tonganus* harem composition in two trees in Olovalu Crater, Tutuila Island. Both the numbers of bats within a harem and the individual females present (deduced from their reproductive status) changed over time. The presence of three adult males and only one female on 22 February 1993 at a former harem site signalled the breakdown of that harem.

Harems in portions of 14 different trees were mapped and checked on subsequent visits from February 1993 to August 1994. Harems censused at intervals of 2 weeks or longer were arbitrarily treated as independent data sets and the minimum number of female bats censused on a day was used when determining harem size.

As population size may influence behavior we estimated the number of flying-foxes on Tutuila Island by visiting all known roosts within a single day four times a year. We circled the island by boat to reach sites inaccessible by vehicle or on foot. In addition, roost exit counts were made at dusk in Olovalu Crater to compare with diurnal estimates.

RESULTS

Social System

Pteropus tonganus roosted predominantly in large colonies consisting of harem groups (one male defending more than one female; Figure 2) and peripheral groups of single adult and juvenile males or groups of males on trees surrounding the reproductive groups. In addition, we occasionally observed single bats and small groups of bats (less than 10 individuals) roosting away from larger colonies. Harems of *P. tonganus* averaged 5.3 ± 2.7 (SD) females per male (range 2-16 females/male; $n = 102$ harems). This sex ratio is not representative of the overall population, however, but applies only to harem trees. Spacing between adjacent females within harems averaged 0.97 ± 0.9 (SD) body lengths (24.2 cm, $n = 33$). Composition of harems in terms of absolute numbers of females and in numbers of females with different-sized young varied from visit to visit (Figure 2).

Harem males appeared to scent-mark their roost territories by vigorously rubbing the neck and shoulder area on branches and leaves. They marked the periphery of their territories along a branch or tree trunk at two or more places adjacent to the females both before departure and upon returning to the roost. Harems were typically found in trees devoid of leaves. In some cases they were located in areas on dead branches. However, in live trees we observed males remove leaves from defended areas. Each evening females departed from the harem tree for foraging sites and returned just prior to dawn. Harem-holding males departed after the females and were the first bats to return to the harem trees in the

morning. Thus, harem-holding males were present both when females departed and returned.

Males defended harems by posturing with an erect penis and by aggressively chasing intruding males. Males "patrolled" their harems by moving among the females. Males were not able to force females to remain within their harems and we witnessed females leaving harems and flying away when a male became persistently aggressive. On one occasion a female was repeatedly approached by a male who attempted to copulate with her. After several minutes of interactions the female left the harem branch and crawled into an adjacent male's harem. The new male greeted her by smelling her and then prevented the other male from following her into his marked territory.

Males appeared to periodically check the receptivity of females. We frequently observed males, with an erect penis, moving through a group of segregated females within a harem and sequentially licking the genitals of several females without mounting any of them.

Mating Behavior

A harem-holding male appeared to initiate copulation by crawling toward a female and extending his nose to her shoulder/neck region. Bared-teeth facial sparring ensued. If the female did not box him with her thumbs and wrists, the male generally lowered his head towards her genitals. The male then repeatedly licked her genitals and she appeared to relax. He alternately licked her face and genitals. Soon after he attempted to position himself behind her by spinning her around using one of his thumbs. Next he appeared to bite the back of her neck and/or the upper shoulder area and struggled to attain a position suitable for mating. The penis appeared quite flexible—probing until it entered the vagina. Pelvic thrusting by the male ensued. The female vocalized (distinct vocalizations only heard during copulation) and struggled (her head was outstretched and her eyes bulged) during the biting and insertion phase. Upon dismounting, the male alternately licked her genitals and his penis several times.

Pairs tended to copulate more than once in quick succession. We observed 119 mating series in detail (Table 1). We defined a mating series as one or several intromission attempts by a pair within a brief time span. A male mounted a given female numerous

Reproductive Condition of Female	Number of Observations	Percentage of Successful Copulations
Female not pregnant or lactating	52	90.3%
Female pregnant	3	33.3%
Female with small young	43	86.0%
Female with medium young	14	57.1%
Female with large young	7	57.1%

Table 1. Success of copulation attempts with female *Pteropus tonganus* of various reproductive status on American Samoa. Table is based on a total of 97 successful and 22 unsuccessful copulation attempts.

times (mean 3.7 intromission episodes; range 1-12 intromission episodes) in relatively quick succession, spanning, on average 6.8 min (range 2-15 min). The duration of each intromission episode averaged 21.4 sec \pm 14.5 SD ($n = 37$). Thus, one mating series may represent up to 12 intromission episodes. In 22 cases (18.5%), the female repulsed the male by facial sparring and thumb/wrist motions. Ninety-seven (81.5%) attempts were considered successful (judged as successful if penile insertion or pelvic thrusts were seen). We acknowledge that sperm may not be transferred during intromission; however, the males generally licked their penis after each intromission episode. On one occasion a male successfully mounted two females carrying small young in his harem within four minutes.

Of the 97 apparently successful copulations, 51.5% were with females that were either pregnant or nursing dependent young (Table 1). The one copulation that involved an obviously pregnant female was probably a forced mating. The male was unusually aggressive and the female vocalized repeatedly. When she broke away she moved up a branch for a distance of 0.6 m with the male in pursuit and flew away while the male remained on the tree branch. Forty-nine successful copulations were post-partum copulations, involving a male mating with a female with dependent young attached. Thirty-seven (75.5% of post-partum matings) involved females with small young.

Copulation attempts with non-pregnant/non-lactating females were most often successful (Chi-Square = 33.9, $df = 1$, $P < 0.001$) as were those involving females with small young (Chi-Square =

22.3, $df = 1$, $P < 0.001$). No significant differences were found between successful and unsuccessful attempts involving pregnant females, females with medium-sized young and females with large young. Of successful post-partum mating attempts, most occurred by males mating with females carrying small young (Table 1). Thus, mating attempts with non-pregnant females and those with smaller young were most often successful. During post-partum copulations, the young typically remained attached to the ventrum of the female. We did not witness any young being dislodged and falling to the ground during mating.

Parturition

Eleven births were observed; January (1), June (3), July (1), and August (6). In addition, females with swollen abdomens and exhibiting contractions were observed in January (1), July (2) and August (1). Pregnant, non-contracting females were observed in Olovalu Crater during all months of the year except April, November and December (no bats were at this roost during the latter two months). During 9 parturitions the mother hung by her feet. Two females alternated between hanging vertically and assuming a cradle position (hung by thumb claws and feet) during delivery. During birth, a whitish slowly pulsating bulge (amniotic sac) appeared at the vaginal orifice. This area was repeatedly licked by the female. The infant's head appeared first. The eyes were open, the newborn yawned, and licked itself about the face. During four births, the time elapsed from the first protrusion of the head to the expulsion of the remainder of the body was 11, 36, 37, and 55 min. The pelage of the newborn offspring is pigmented dorsally like the adult of its species.

After each birth event, the mother ate the umbilical cord and placenta.

In one difficult or breech birth, all of the body except the left wing was expelled. The baby was unable to extract its wing over the next 139 minutes (at which point the observations were terminated). No females from the same harem nor from neighbouring harems assisted during this difficult birth. However, the harem male approached and was repelled by the delivering female.

Development of the Young

Young in the day roost clung to mothers nearly continually until they were about 1/2 adult length at which point they spent increasingly longer periods hanging by themselves near the mother and often wrapped within the female's wings. Mothers readily flew with medium young clinging to their venter. Larger young were generally not transported to feeding areas at night but were left hanging within the harem tree. Many of the larger young took flight and departed shortly after the females flew off. Unattended young did not creche at night and we did not see adults remain behind with the young. Young began to fly when their body length was between 1/2 and 3/4 that of adults. The smallest volant young (about 3/4 adult length) captured in a mist net away

from a roost weighed 210 g (ca. 50 % of mean adult mass) with a forearm of 122mm (ca. 87% of mean adult forearm length).

Reproductive Chronology and Sites

Olovalu Crater served as a major nursery and mating roost. Most female *P. tonganus* in Olovalu Crater were pregnant or nursing dependent young from February to late October 1993 and January to August 1994 (Fig. 3). The size of young present in this roost in late October and upon their return in early January suggests that *P. tonganus* is reproductively active year-round. On many occasions >70 % of all females within harems were either pregnant or nursing young (Figs. 3, 4). Pregnant bats were observed in Olovalu Crater during all months (except November and December of 1993 and April and July of 1994 when no bats were present) with a peak in August. Females nursing small young were observed during every month of the year (except when no bats were present in November and December of 1993 and April and July of 1994) in Olovalu Crater (Fig. 3). However, bimodal peaks in small young occurred during January-March and May-August. Thus, reproductive activities (pregnancy, parturition, and presence of small young) occurred throughout the year with activity peaks in January and August.

ROOSTS	Dec 92	Mar 93	Aug 93	Nov 93	Feb 94	Jun 94
Fagatele	0	0	0	0	0	0
Taputapu	0	13	0	0	0	0
Nuomanu/Taufanua	50	700	50	0	900	800
Tolotolooleoti	125	0	600	1350	0	0
Siliaga Point	150	150	350	600	250	800
Agalua Rock	50	0	130	0	0	0
Leutu Point	60	0	0	0	0	0
Puaneva Point	120	0	0	500	350	300
Polauta Point	60	0	0	0	0	0
Cape Larsen	0	30	0	0	0	0
Samitutu Point	0	70	0	0	0	0
Olomoana Mountain	0	0	300	0	200	100
Olovalu Crater	0	893	1181	823	1627	830
Fagatogo	0	0	400	0	0	400
Faiga Ridge	0	0	0	20	0	0
Oa Valley	0	0	0	0	300	400
TOTALS	615	1856	3011	3293	3627	3630

Table 2. Quarterly population counts of *Pteropus tonganus* at all known daytime roosts on Tutuila, American Samoa. The traditional roost at Fagatele was abandoned in December 1991 because of cyclone Val.

Olovalu Crater was not the only day roost site on Tutuila used as a mating/nursery location. Non-volant young with adult females were seen at other foraging and roosting sites on Tutuila during every month of the year.

Population Counts

Quarterly censuses of flying-foxes at roosts between December 1992 and June 1994 documented increasing populations on Tutuila Island (Table 2). *P. tonganus* exhibited high roost-site fidelity in undisturbed areas, but occasionally relocated to traditional sites nearby (Table 2). Roost exit counts at Olovalu Crater were similar to daytime roost counts.

DISCUSSION

Social System

The mating system of *P. tonganus* appeared to have elements of both female defence polygyny and resource defence polygyny (Emlen and Oring 1977). Males used threats, fights, and scent marking to space themselves and to exclude other males from tree branches. Females within a harem are defended from advances by other males. Females occasionally moved from one harem to another. Harems averaged 5.3 females per male (range 2-16 females). Harems appeared to fluctuate in absolute numbers of females within a harem over a period of weeks (Fig. 2). It is not known how these harems form. The males maintaining harems mated with many of the females present. The harem site does not appear to be related to female foraging sites. Females departed from the roost independently of other females and may travel many kilometres to foraging sites at night (Banack 1996). Colonial roosting and the polygynous mating system are probably not due to predation pressure. On American Samoa the only native predator of flying-foxes is the barn owl (*Tyto alba*) and predation events appear to be rare and occur primarily at night (Grant and Banack 1995). The sympatric *P. samoensis* is monogamous and territorial in the same habitats (Craig *et al.* 1994; Banack 1996). Perhaps by joining a harem group, females avoid aggressive sexual advances by other males and mate with only those males able to hold harem territories. Harem trees appeared similar in quality, visibility, and safety from predators to those sites used in nearby trees by bachelor males.

Pteropus tonganus is strongly colonial, occurring in roosts of up to several thousand bats. Of the 41 species and subspecies of flying foxes tabulated by Pierson and Rainey (1992), 33 (80%) were strongly to moderately colonial. Harem systems have been documented for *P. seychellensis comorensis* (Cheke and Dahl 1981), *P. rodricensis* (Carroll and Mace 1988), *P. m. mariannus* (Wiles 1987), and perhaps *P. giganteus* (Neuweiler 1969).

Pteropus mariannus and *P. tonganus* displayed similar social behaviour and reproductive patterns. Wiles (1987) reported that 69-80 % of the members of the *P. mariannus* colony in Guam roosted in harems containing a male and 2-15 females. In addition, the numbers of females within harems fluctuated over a span of several days (Wiles 1987).

Mating and Parturition

Pteropus tonganus displayed year-round reproduction from November 1992 to August 1994 on Tutuila, American Samoa (Fig. 3). Aseasonality, as observed in *P. tonganus*, may reflect current environmental conditions. Populations of *P. tonganus* were reduced to 80-90 % of their former numbers due to the effects of three cyclones and subsequent overharvesting by humans (Craig *et al.* 1994). Val (wind speed up to 240 km/hr) defoliated, snapped, and uprooted many trees in Western and American Samoa in December 1991 (Elmqvist *et al.* 1994). Many bats starved when food resources (flowers and fruit) were stripped from the trees by the strong winds of the recent cyclones (including Val). Flying-foxes entered villages in search of food and some were foraging on the ground. Many bats were taken by dogs, pigs, and humans (Craig *et al.* 1994; Pierson *et al.* 1996). Some vegetative recovery was rapid and food resources were abundant during our study (Trail, unpubl. data; Banack 1998). Pierson *et al.* (1996) reported seeing no baby bats during their visit to American Samoa immediately after the passage of Cyclone Val (December 1991). We first saw small dependent young (post-cyclone) on 1 September 1992. Assuming a gestation period of about 6 months (reviewed by Pierson and Rainey 1992), conception probably occurred in March (about 3 months after the storm). Although 48.5% of all successful copulations observed from August 1992-August 1994 involved non-pregnant or non-lactating females, 62.5% of those occurred in 1992

(Fig. 5) at a time when the population was still recovering from the effects of Cyclone Val.

Copulations with lactating females occurred more frequently in 1993 and 1994 as food availability increased during the vegetative recovery following cyclone Val (Trail, unpubl. data; Banack 1998). At this time we can only speculate as to whether the current reproductive patterns are typical for *P. tonganus* or a temporary response to low population density and high food availability. *Pteropus tonganus* may also breed year-round on Niue (Wodzicki and Felten 1975; Grant 1994). *Pteropus m. mariannus* on Guam exhibited a similar pattern of year-round reproduction under severe population declines and abundant food resources (Wiles 1987).

The aseasonal reproductive behavior observed in *P. tonganus* is not typical of most *Pteropus* species. Australian flying foxes (*Pteropus* spp.) are seasonal breeders (Ratcliffe 1932; Nelson 1965, Puddicombe 1981; Martin *et al.* 1987). Equatorial *P. giganteus* mate from early December to early January and gave birth in late May / early June (Marshall 1947). In Vanuatu, *P. t. geddiei* conceived in

February and March and gave birth in August and September (Baker and Baker 1936).

Because *P. tonganus* exhibited year-round reproduction and frequent copulations with lactating females, it may be possible for *P. tonganus* to produce young at about 9-month intervals, depending on whether, and how extensively, lactation overlaps with gestation. Megachiroptera appear to lack a lactational anoestrus (O'Brien 1993). It is also possible that a nursing female may store sperm and exhibit delayed fertilization, delayed implantation, or delayed development until lactation ceases (O'Brien 1993). Although bats in the genus *Pteropus* are believed to produce just one young a year (reviewed by Pierson and Rainey 1992), Falanruw (1988) reported that *P. m. yapensis* may produce young within a shorter time; approximately one baby per 9 months. *Pteropus m. yapensis* breeds year-round and exhibits frequent post-partum copulations similar to *P. tonganus*. Pregnancy is believed to last 4-6 months and nursing 5-6 months for most *Pteropus* sp. (reviewed in Martin *et al.* 1987). In addition, superfoetation (two fetuses apparently of different age from separate conceptions) may increase reproductive output

Figure 5. Percent of copulations involving female *Pteropus tonganus* of various reproductive status in American Samoa in 1992-1994. Fractions in legend box denote relative length of dependent young.

(Martin *et al.* 1987; Martin *et al.* 1995). Anatomical reproductive studies or long-term studies of marked individuals are needed to elucidate the internal reproductive events in these bats.

Parturition behavior including the duration of the pause period in *P. tonganus* is similar to that reported for *P. poliocephalus* by Nelson (1965) and Martin *et al.* (1987). It is interesting that the single breached birth by *P. tonganus* reported in this paper was not assisted by helpers. Helpers or "midwives" have helped with single birth events in captive populations of both *P. rodricensis* (Kunz *et al.* 1992) and *P. conspicillatus* (Spencer, pers. comm.).

Roost Patterns

Olovalu Crater has been in nearly continuous use since personnel of the Department of Marine and Wildlife Resources in American Samoa began keeping records in 1987. Bats tended to roost in harems, and in predominantly male bachelor groups, or singly (males only) on the periphery of the colony. This structure and composition persisted throughout the year and is highly similar to *P. mariannus* in Guam, The Commonwealth of the Northern Mariana Islands (CNMI), and Yap (Wiles 1987).

Roost shifts in *P. tonganus* and *P. m. mariannus* have been associated with resource availability and human disturbance on both Tutuila and Rota, CNMI respectively (Banack 1996, Taisican pers. comm.). It is unclear if the high ratio of reproductive females in Olovalu Crater is representative of the island wide population or represents a congregation of reproductive individuals of *P. tonganus*. The presence of sub-adult males in bachelor groups within the crater and females with young in other roosts support the idea that the aggregation within the crater is not unique. Wiles (1987) reported that a small portion of the *P. mariannus* population on Guam roosts solitarily or in small groups; an observation consistent with our records of *P. tonganus*. Protected colony sites in Guam continue to shelter bats while usage of other sites in Guam and the Northern Mariana Islands have declined or ceased, due to heavy poaching and harvesting for food (Wiles 1987).

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